

MULTIPLE IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE FUSELAGE PANEL

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the post-impact behaviour of composite fuselage panels subjected to multi-site low-velocity impacts. Large curved stiffened panels (1.2m x 0.8m, with composite skins/stiffeners and aluminum frames) of two different skin thicknesses were subjected to sequential drop-weight impacts at locations previously determined to be critical in finite element (FE) simulations. After assessment of the impact damage each panel was tested in compression. High speed video, strain gauges, Digital Image Correlation and acoustic emission were used to monitor the failure development and to provide data for comparison with the FE simulations. The FE models, which were based on a mesomechanical approach, showed a good agreement with both the impact damage and the subsequent compression performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this study is to investigate the post-impact behaviour of aircraft-grade carbon/epoxy curved stiffened panels containing multi-site impact damage that may arise, for example, in a hail storm. Delaminations and debonding at the skin-stiffener interface created by impact can grow under compression bringing about global collapse of the stiffened panel. This process can be significantly promoted by local buckling of sublaminates created by the delaminations and of the skin laminate separated from the stiffener by debonding. Other compressive failure mechanisms include global buckling, local-global buckling and in-plane failure due to stress concentrations.

The study included an experimental programme consisting of multi-site impact and compression-after-impact testing of curved composite stiffened panels of two different thicknesses. The impact locations and energies were determined after detailed FE modelling, in which a multi-step analysis was used to simulate the impacts and the compression after impact (CAI) test. After carrying out the impacts and the associated damage assessment on a panel, the panel was tested to failure in compression. During the CAI test various items of monitoring and data collection equipment were used to help characterise the failure process and provide data for comparison with FE predictions.

2 BRIEF DETAILS OF THE STIFFENED PANELS

A schematic drawing of a panel can be seen in Figure 1. The panels had an overall size of 1150mm x 790mm with a curvature radius of 1978mm. The material of the skin and the omega profile stiffeners was the T800/M21 carbon epoxy system. Two different thicknesses were produced of the multidirectional skins and stiffeners. The thinner skin and thinner stiffeners were used to produce a panel later identified as 'thin' with a skin thickness of 1.7mm; similarly the thicker skin and stiffeners were used to produce a 'thick' panel with skin thickness of 3.6mm. Reinforcing plies of woven carbon fibre prepreg to ABS 5003N0000 were placed in strips on the inner and outer surfaces at each end of the panel in order to ensure that there was no premature failure due to stress concentrations associated with the load introduction. The proper load transfer was ensured by potting the ends of the panels with glass fibre reinforced epoxy resin. Finally the representative structural aluminum frames and the aluminum clips were used to support the panels from out of plane displacements during testing.

Figure 1 Overview of the panel with its parts; skin (yellow), stiffeners (red), reinforcing plies (blue), potting (gold) and aluminum frames and clips (green-grey).

3 PRELIMINARY FE AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON COUPONS

The first studies were made on standard coupons (150 mm x 100 mm) [1] with two different thicknesses and layups matching those of the two different panel skins. FE analyses were performed to predict the residual strength in compression of the coupons after multiple impacts and these predictions were validated against experimental test data. The horizontally aligned impacts were carried out at co-ordinates (mm from the centre) [-25,0] or [-25,0] & [15,0], or [-25,0] & [25,0]. The vertically aligned impacts were at co-ordinates, in mm, [0,-25] or [0,-25] & [0,15] or [0,-25] & [0,25]. A schematic of the impact locations can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Schematic of the impact locations

Finite element (FE) models using ABAQUS were developed in order to simulate the low velocity impacts (LVI) on the coupons, any interaction between multiple areas of damage and the compression-after-impact (CAI) performance of the coupons. A FE model of the thin and thick coupons was

developed using continuum shell elements. Layers of cohesive elements were inserted between sublaminates in order to model delamination initiation and growth during impacts, Figure 3. An energy-based damage model developed at Imperial College London [2] and implemented into the Abaqus FE system as a user material damage subroutine [3, 4], was employed to predict translaminar damage. The subroutine is based on a continuum damage mechanics approach and can predict four failure modes; tensile fibre fracture, compressive fibre fracture, coupled in-plane shear-tensile matrix fracture (quadratic criterion) and coupled in-plane shear-compressive matrix fracture.

Figure 3 FE model for simulating low-velocity multi-site impact and CAI tests

The FE model was defined as a multiple-step analysis as follows:

1. Impact step: a sphere defined as a rigid body (mass=2.41 kg) was propelled onto the plate with an energy of 10J.
2. Damping step: to dissipate the kinetic energy of the plate, a viscous pressure was applied over the plate.
3. Steps 1 and 2 are repeated for each further impact.
4. Compression step: Once the plate has stopped vibrating after the final impact, the plate was compressed in the longitudinal direction. The out-of-plane displacement of the plates was constrained during compression by a set of straight bars that represent the support provided by the CAI test fixture.

The experimental results are compared with the FE predictions in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Experimental results against the FE predictions for coupons

4 FE OF STIFFENED PANELS

Using the same technique, the detailed FE model of the curved panel was developed and can be seen in Fig. 5. The impact scenarios determined using the FE model are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 5

Detailed FE model of the panel with boundary conditions used during the multistep analysis.

	Panel	TN-pr	TN-sc0	TN-sc1	TN-sc2
	Energy [J]	-	25	25	40
thin	Impact positions				
	Panel	TK-pr	TK sc1	TK sc2	
	Energy [J]	-	58	58	
thick	Impact positions				

Table 1 Impact scenarios (all impacts were on the outer surface of the panels)

4 TESTING THE PANELS

The key tasks of the test campaign are summarized in Table 2. The first step was to prepare the panel; the panel was c-scanned, strain gauges were placed in the predefined positions and a speckle pattern was sprayed on the outer surface for monitoring with a digital image correlation (DIC) system during the CAI testing. The impact tests were performed using a CEAAT drop tower, Figure 6, with CEAAT 6.01 software controlling the test procedure and recording the test data. Each panel was placed in the base of the tower designed to ensure the correct location of the impacts. The impact scenarios that were investigated are summarized in Table 1.

After each impact the panel was inspected by using a portable ultra sound scanner to verify the damage size that was introduced in the panel. A hyper-stiff 2500kN compression machine was used in order to compression test the panels to failure. This has been modified with a specially designed framework to provide out-of-plane support to the ring frame members and to the free edges of the skin.

Prior to testing	Impact testing	CAI testing
Perform ultrasound inspection Mount strain gauges Spray speckle pattern for digital image correlation (DIC)	Record force - time history Perform ultrasound inspection	Record applied load and displacement (LVDT) Record strain (strain gauges) Capture images for DIC (for displacement & strain field) Record acoustic emission (AE) signals for damage classification High speed camera recording (for crack initiation/propagation) High definition video (to monitor overall behaviour)

Table 2 Summary of key tasks during the panel test campaign

During the CAI tests, HD video and high speed camera (HSC) recording, strain gauges, DIC and acoustic emission (AE) monitoring were used to monitor the failure development and provide data for comparison with the FE simulations. The HSC was used in order to capture the initiation and propagation of the cracks. The strain gauges were used to monitor the strain variations and were correlated with the DIC data, which also provided information on the displacements and any local buckling. Finally the damage classification during the CAI was assessed by using acoustic emission. Typical output of the CAI tests is shown in Figure 7 and in Figure 8 a summary of the experimentally measured CAI failure loads is presented.

Figure 6: Panel preparation and testing set up

Figure 7: Typical output from CAI testing:
 top left, a CAI tested panel, indicating locations of the impacts,
 top right, the high speed camera captures the initiation of the crack from the impacted area,
 bottom right, the DIC records of the skin vertical and out-of-plane displacements,
 bottom left, the classification of the damage made using the acoustic emission data.

5 COMPARISON OF TEST RESULTS WITH THE FE MODELS

Figure 8 includes the FE-predicted failure loads for the CAI tests and Figure 9 presents experimental and predicted data of the damage and force response during impact and CAI testing. The FE models accurately predicted the damage size of the skin delaminations and the skin/stiffener debond area caused by the impacts and the force-time response is also well predicted. For the CAI behavior, the FE models successfully predicted the magnitude of the loss in strength of the panels is well predicted as is the location of the failure initiation and its propagation path. The CAI failure load predictions are more accurate for the thin panels as can be seen Figure 8 and further studies are being conducted to explore the influence of various FE model refinements (such as cohesive elements to capture delamination growth within the stiffener feet).

Figure 8: Experimentally measured and FE-predicted CAI failure loads.

Impact comparison

CAI comparison

Figure 9: Comparison between the FE prediction for impacts (example of an impact above a stiffener foot where delamination and dis-bond occurs) and CAI final failure of TN-sc1.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the behaviours observed during multi-site impact and compression-after-impact testing of curved composite stiffened panels of two different thicknesses and compares these behaviours to FE predictions. The test jigs worked well and the panels failed in a valid manner. The experiments demonstrated the influence of energy, location and number of multi-site impacts on the compressive residual strength. FE model predictions showed good agreement with the experimental data for the impact response and for the subsequent compression behaviour, and can be used to identify critical multi-site impact scenarios.

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